

Notes

Chemical examination of the flowers of *Saraca indica*

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SARACA indica (N.O. Leguminosae). *Uses*—Medicinal¹. *Previous work*—Several workers have investigated other parts²⁻⁶. *Present work*—Air dried flowers were successively extracted with hot petroleum ether, ethylacetate and 95% alcohol. A yellow deposit obtained in all the three extracts was filtered.

The yellow deposit on chromatography over neutral alumina followed by preparative T.L.C. yielded compound A which was identified as β -sitosterol.

The ethylacetate and alcoholic extracts on column chromatography over silica gel afforded compounds B, C, D and E. Compound B was found to be identical with quercetin⁷. Compounds C, D and E were flavone glycosides and were identified as Kaempferol-3-O- β -D-glucoside⁸, quercetin-3-O- β -D-glucoside⁹ and apigenin-7-O- β -D-glucoside¹⁰ respectively from a study of u.v. spectral data, identical m.p., m.m.p. and degradations.

Tanins, catechins and leucoyanins were also found in its alcoholic extract and were not studied in detail.

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Chemical examination of the flowers of *Grewia-asiatica* Linn.

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GREWIA asiatica Linn. (N.O. Tiliaceae). *Uses*: Medicinal¹. *Previous work*—On stem cuttings², seed oil³ and stem bark⁴. *Present work*—Air dried flowers were extracted with hot alcohol, filtered and kept for few days. A yellow deposit was obtained, filtered and the concentrated filtrate was extracted successively with petroleum ether, ethylacetate, acetone and ethanol. The yellow deposit was also fractionated into petroleum ether, ethylacetate soluble fractions and mixed with petroleum ether and ethylacetate extracts obtained as above. The petroleum ether extract on column chromatography over neutral alumina afforded compounds A, D, E and F. The ethylacetate extract on column chromatography on silica gel yielded compounds B, C, G and H.

Compound A was identified as β -sitosterol⁵ (m.p., m.m.p., superimposable IR) and compound B was found to be identical with quercetin⁶. Compound C, C₂₂H₂₂O₁₁, m.p. 294°-6° and compound G, C₂₁H₂₂O₁₀, m.p. 225°-6° was identified as quercetin 3-O- β -D-glucoside⁷ and Naringenin-7-O- β -D-glucoside⁸ respectively from the studies of their u.v. spectral data, degradations, m.p. and mixed m.p. The compound H, m.p. 248°-51° was characterized as Naringenin⁹. Besides these four amino acids namely proline, lysine, glutaric acid and phenyl alanine and three free sugars, namely, glucose, xylose and arabinose were identified by paper Co-chromatography with authentic samples in acetone and ethanol extracts. Work on other compounds is in progress.

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Chemical examination of seeds of *Amomum subulatum*

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AMOMUM subulatum (family Zingiberaceae).
Uses—Medicinal¹. Previous work—Ash contents of seeds². Present work—Powdered seeds were extracted with hot petroleum ether (40°–60°), then successively with cold methanolic hydrochloric acid (2%), ethylacetate and hot alcohol.

The petroleum ether extract gave viscous oil, hence was rejected. The 2% cold methanolic extract on column chromatography over silica gel followed by paper chromatography yielded compound A. The concentrated ethylacetate and ethanolic extracts both gave a creamish white deposit which on chromatography over silica gel yielded compound B along with few minor substances.

From a study of u.v. spectral data, degradation, m.p., m.m.p. the compound A, C₂₈H₃₃O₁₇, m.p. > 300° was identified as petunidin 3,5-diglucoside and the compound B, C₂₁H₂₄O₁₂, m.p. 230° (dec.) was identified as Leucocyanidin-3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside. Studies on minor substances are in progress.

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Lead-*n*-butyl thioglycolate complexes—A polarographic study

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IN this communication, composition and stability constants of Pb²⁺-*n*-butyl thioglycolate complexes have been investigated in 50% dimethyl formamide (D.M.F.) media polarographically. The values of ΔG, ΔH and ΔS are also reported.

Experimental

n-Butyl thioglycolate (referred herein as RSH) was supplied by Evan's Chemitics Inc., N.Y. and all other chemicals were AnalaR (B.D.H.). Freshly prepared solutions of the ligand and others were used to avoid the effect of ageing and air oxidation. NaClO₄ and Triton X-100 were used as supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor respectively. All solutions used for recording polarograms had in addition to RSH, a lead ion concentration of 1.00 mM, 0.1M NaClO₄ and 0.002% triton X-100 in 50% D.M.F. media. The entire study was carried out at a constant ionic strength μ = 0.1M NaClO₄ and at a pH 4.30 ± 0.04 maintained by adding 5.00 ml of Clark's and Lub's buffer of pH 4.2. The concentration of RSH varied from 0.004 to 0.012M.

A manual polarograph in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell was used for recording the polarograms against S.C.E. as a reference electrode in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The capillary had the following characteristics

$$m = 1.107 \text{ mg/sec.}, t = 4.85 \text{ sec. at } -0.3 \text{ Volt vs. S.C.E.}$$

Results and Discussion

The plot of i_d vs. $h^{1/2} i_{eff}$ yielded a straight line showing the diffusion controlled nature of the waves.

The plots of $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs. $E_{d.e.}$ were also linear whose